

Design and Definition of Transnational Access Calls

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1. Introduction

The AQUARIUS project will provide Transnational Access (TA) to a broad range of research infrastructures (RIs) to support the development phase of the EU Mission to Restore our Ocean and waters by 2030, the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership, the European Green Deal, and international climate initiatives. 57 research infrastructure services will be accessible, such as vessels, platforms, aircraft, drones, satellite, sensors, observatories, test sites, facilities, and data infrastructures.

Similar to previous projects with a TA programme (e.g., EUROFLEETS 1, 2 & Plus; ARICE; INTERACCESS; JERICO, JERICO-NEXT, JERICO-S3 and ASSEMBLE Plus), researchers will access the infrastructures through a TA funding programme.

This programme will foster the use of research infrastructures across different domains and countries, focusing on specific themes and regions, in line with the Lighthouse Regions: the Baltic and the North Sea Basins, Black Sea, Atlantic/Arctic, and Mediterranean Sea and their rivers.

Design and Definition of Transnational Access Calls

AQUARIUS work package (WP) 3 is dedicated to the design, development and management of the TA Programme. Task 3.2, TA Call Design and Development will define the call programme, eligibility criteria, and funding conditions to meet the various challenges for and expectations of both RIs and the research community.

The overall objectives of the TA Programme are to:

- Enhance the quality and efficiency of research and innovation activities by enabling cross-disciplinary and cross-border collaboration and exchange of knowledge, data, and skills.
- Increase the visibility and accessibility of research infrastructures by facilitating the dissemination and sharing of RI information, resources, and best practices.
- Support the sustainability and competitiveness of research infrastructures by stimulating the demand and utilization of RI facilities and services, and by encouraging the involvement and feedback of RI users and stakeholders.

Based on this and according to D3.1, the AQUARIUS TA programme will support research projects from any scientific discipline and thematic area relevant to the Lighthouse Regions and the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters, listed below and reported in **Figure 1**.

- The Atlantic and Arctic coast, covering the North Atlantic Ocean, the Norwegian Sea, the Greenland Sea, the Barents Sea and the Arctic Ocean.
- The Baltic and North Sea, covering the Baltic Sea, the North Sea, the English Channel and the Skagerrak and Kattegat straits.
- The Mediterranean Sea, covering the Mediterranean Sea and its sub-regions, such as the Adriatic Sea, the Aegean Sea, the Ionian Sea, the Tyrrhenian Sea, the Ligurian Sea, the Balearic Sea, the Alboran Sea and the Levantine Sea.
- The Danube River basin, covering the Danube River and its tributaries, such as the Sava, the Drava, the Tisza, the Prut and the Dniester.

Figure 1. Regions for EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030"

Furthermore, the programme will encourage **interdisciplinary, transdisciplinary and participatory approaches** that involve researchers from different fields and sectors, as well as stakeholders from the public, private and civil society.

In this framework, D3.3 aims to design the AQUARIUS TA Programme, based on best practices and experiences from similar projects.

The document covers the following aspects:

- The scientific scope of TA Programme, including timing
- The definition of two AQUARIUS TA calls
- The eligibility and access conditions for TA applicants and providers
- Funding conditions

2. Call description

The AQUARIUS TA Programme aims to:

- Support research and innovation projects that **contribute to the goals and challenges of the Lighthouse Regions and the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters.**
- Provide researchers with **access to state-of-the-art facilities, equipment, data, samples, expertise and networks** of the Lighthouse Regions.

- **Facilitate the mobility, training and networking** of researchers across the Lighthouse Regions and beyond.
- **Enhance the visibility, impact and dissemination of the research outcomes and best practices** of the Lighthouse Regions.
- **Strengthen the cooperation and synergies** among the Lighthouse Regions and other relevant initiatives and stakeholders of the ocean and waters.

The TA Programme design targets both scientific and societal challenges and opportunities for **research infrastructure integration** based on:

- the level of heterogeneity of the facilities (i.e. fixed and mobile)
- the ocean, freshwater, and environmental variables measured (i.e. physical, chemical and biological, geophysical)
- their geographical coverage
- the disciplines addressed

To foster the integration, we encourage proposals that involve multiple infrastructures and promote comprehensive research approaches.

To achieve this, the TA Programme design benefits from the outcome of Task 3.1 - Analysis of Challenges across Marine and Freshwater, which includes an analysis of knowledge deficit and data gaps, and Task 6.1 - Analysis of Data Gaps. These tasks will provide input to Task 3.3 - Integration of Access Procedures and Call Implementation.

Within the TA Programme, two different calls will be launched, extending the infrastructure to new users and increasing the overall number of users.

Call 1 – Regional Lighthouse Access Call

Call 1 will prioritise themes, scientific and societal challenges in the EU Lighthouse Regions. In [deliverable 3.1](#), AQUARIUS has listed the scientific and societal priorities and challenges that are of particular focus in the respective Lighthouse Regions.

The Regional Lighthouse Access Call will be based on the four Lighthouse Regions, including cross-cutting Lighthouse Regions where thematically appropriate. For each region, several lines of action are defined as shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1 – Lines of Action of the first AQUARIUS TA call

Lighthouse Region	Line of Action
Atlantic-Artic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable management of marine resources • Protection of marine ecosystems • Climate change impact assessment
Danube River	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of water quality, biodiversity and habitats • Prevention of floods and droughts
Mediterranean Sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancement of marine biodiversity • Mitigation of marine pollution • Development of blue tourism and aquaculture
Baltic & North Sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of nutrient and chemical pollution • Restoration of marine habitats • Promotion of circular economy and green shipping

The lines of action will address the scientific and societal challenges reported in D3.1 and are summarized in **Table 2** and **Table 3** respectively.

Table 2 – Scientific challenges within the Lighthouses Region

Lighthouses Region	Scientific challenges
Atlantic-Artic region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying land-ocean continuum for protection and restoration of key marine and river ecosystems in the Atlantic/Arctic • Designing and implementing cost-effective methods for monitoring Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) to support conservation measures, ensuring these efforts are efficient and impactful in preserving biodiversity and ecosystem health • Understanding biodiversity changes due to climate change and anthropogenic pressures • Improving knowledge on the interaction between species
Danube River	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing research-development and innovation capabilities in the Lower Danube regions (knowledge transfer from the Upper Danube region where there are some of the most important European RDI hubs) • Developing, testing and implementing at river basin scale active, passive and nature-based solutions for freshwater and marine ecosystems restoration • Developing, testing and implementing nature-based solutions for mitigating the effects of extreme phenomena (drought, floods, heavy storms, etc.) • Better assessment of the cumulative effects of natural and anthropogenic pressures on freshwater and marine ecosystems, as well as the local communities' welfare. • Harmonizing methods for assessing significant pressures related to disconnected wetlands/floodplains and further implementing monitoring for identifying negative impacts of disconnected wetlands/floodplains on biological quality elements.
Mediterranean Sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing innovative technologies for early detection and response to oil and hazardous substances pollution incidents • Enhancing biodiversity monitoring and conservation efforts to safeguard unique marine species and habitats • Integrating data from various sources to improve understanding of ecosystem dynamics and resilience in the face of environmental stressors • Advancing research on the interactions between human activities and marine environments to inform sustainable management practices
Baltic & North Sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cumulative impacts of multistressors (e.g. high nutrients, low oxygen, increase of temperature, contaminants, acidification, noise, dissolved organic matter) on marine biodiversity and ecosystem functioning are poorly studied and the effects of increasing use of marine space on environmental conditions may strengthen these • Side effects of fisheries and aquaculture on marine food-webs and habitats require attention to avoid unwanted feedback on marine productivity • Supporting aquaculture by providing reliable warning systems for biological (harmful algae), chemical (oxygen depletion) or physical (heat waves, storms) hazards. Similar services may support fisheries, recreation and tourism industry • Methods and consequences of using exhausted gas fields as sites for CO₂ storage are under scrutiny. • Understanding how the shift in ship fuels, e.g., from diesel to LNG, or reduction of sulphur in fuels, affects their real emissions and which are the impacts on marine ecosystem. • Can the Blue Economy platforms and related constructions be built up in such a way they promote biodiversity hot spots.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collecting biomaterials (specimen, eDNA) to search for new potentially cultivated marine organisms or for new biotechnology components.
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Table 3 – Societal challenges within the Lighthouses Region

Lighthouses Region	Societal challenges
Atlantic-Artic region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engaging local communities and stakeholders in the Atlantic/Arctic regarding environmental and conservation issues Access to education and resources needed to implement sustainable practices and to contribute to environmental conservation The economic dependence of local communities on activities that harm the environment, such as overfishing, oil and gas extraction, and unsustainable tourism, presents a major societal challenge. Finding alternative, sustainable economic opportunities is essential for reducing environmental impact while supporting local livelihoods Stronger policy support and governance frameworks to effectively protect the Atlantic Arctic environment. This includes the development and enforcement of regulations that balance economic development with environmental sustainability The communities in the Atlantic Arctic are highly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, which can lead to displacement, loss of traditional livelihoods, and health risks. Addressing these vulnerabilities through adaptive strategies and resilience-building measures is a significant societal challenge integrating traditional knowledge with scientific research. Bridging this gap can enhance understanding and management of the Atlantic Arctic environment, ensuring that traditional practices are respected and incorporated into modern conservation efforts Ensuring equity and inclusion in environmental decision-making processes remains a challenge
Danube River	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased public understanding and awareness of the actions needed to protect and restore the degraded habitats/ecosystems within the Danube River Basin. Reducing the disparities in development occurring in the Danube River basin Input and basis for further European, regional and/or national/local legal and policy, documents (in particular for the upcoming EU nature restoration targets, reviews of the Marine Framework Strategy Directive, Water Framework Directive, MSP, updates of the Danube River Management Plan, etc.)
Mediterranean Sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting public awareness and engagement in marine conservation efforts to foster a sense of stewardship among local communities Enhancing collaboration among Mediterranean countries to address shared environmental challenges and achieve common conservation goals Leveraging the Barcelona Convention and its protocols to strengthen regional cooperation and governance for sustainable marine resource management Creating economic opportunities through sustainable blue economy initiatives that balance environmental protection with socio-economic development
Baltic & North Sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finding suitable offshore spaces that combine different activities and uses of the marine space, and to avoid conflicts between different uses Testing multipurpose platforms, also for marine monitoring and research purposes, could be one element supported by AQUARIUS TA calls, including ships, aquaculture sites and wind parks, to name some Marine measurements may be better utilized in creating products and solutions for maritime traffic, e.g., for finding cost-efficient routes (avoiding ice or counter current) Increase of uses in marine space may cause habitat loss and disturbance Societal and economic pressures to have a fast lane for permissions to build-up solutions for green transition may compromise thorough environmental impact assessment. Therefore, it is vital to facilitate

	opening all so-far hidden data, use up-to-date model tools and use all additional opportunities to perform baseline studies at key sites of interest
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A possible scenario in the Mediterranean Sea to address the line of action “Mitigation of marine pollution”

Given that the identification, main traits, and quantification of the major polluting sources (agents) have been identified, the transfer mechanisms and time scales of polluting agents are still not fully understood. This understanding is crucial to provide effective knowledge-based support for policy decisions. The complexity of marine ecosystems poses significant challenges in comprehending the cumulative effects of human activities and identifying effective, feasible, and sustainable interventions to mitigate negative impacts.

Proposal should focus on one or more of the following objectives:

1. Development of new concepts and models to describe ecosystem dynamics, using available data and including land-sea interactions.
2. New sampling and analytical methodologies to support the effectiveness of model results.
3. Interventions to understand and reduce impacts from polluting sources into the marine environment, including revised observational strategies, new recycling/technological innovations and methods, promoting behavioural change, socio-economic analyses to identify of feasible and cost-benefit options.

In this scenario, a potential dedicated TA service would consist of integrating and coupling satellite observations (detecting and visualising hot-spot areas to be investigated on a large scale) with the in-situ coastal observations (e.g. measurements along autonomous straight-line using gliders and/or drones to obtain a spatio-temporal map of homogenous variables also at multiple depths and/or elevations) and offshore observations (e.g. measurements from research vessels to study the gradient variance).

Call 2 – Super-integrated Lighthouse Call

Call 2 will be an ‘adaptive’ and responsive call, shaped by the outcomes of the first call. This second call will focus on new emerging issues, themes not adequately covered in Call 1, or developments within the EU Mission Ocean.

The super-integrated Lighthouse Call is expected to focus more on the key challenges identified for Call 1 that affect more than one of the Lighthouse Regions. This approach will ensure that the Super-integrated Lighthouse Call is even more flexible than Call 1 in terms of cross-cutting topics and regions and can respond to the evolving needs and priorities of the research community and stakeholders.

A possible scenario in the Mediterranean Sea, Danubius river and Baltic & North Sea address to “health of marine ecosystem”

The health of marine ecosystems can be significantly impacted by anthropogenic activities, disrupting their equilibrium. Various sources of pollution, such as CO2 emissions and litter, originating from inland areas—primarily in the Mediterranean and Danube regions—or from marine environments, especially in the Baltic region, can produce diverse effects. Observations, models, and precautionary or mitigation initiatives must be grounded in thorough knowledge. These challenges need to be

addressed with models and innovative indicators to enhance the effectiveness of scientific advice.

Proposals should add value by introducing innovative approaches and actions to address challenges related to the effectiveness and efficiency of scientific support for policy decisions and territorial interventions.

Timing of the call release

- The first call will open on November 11, 2024, and will remain open for at least two months for the submission of proposals. The closing date will be January 20, 2025.
- The second call will open on September 2, 2025, and will remain open for two months. The closing date will be October 28, 2025.

3. Eligibility criteria

Transnational Access will be provided to selected 'user groups'. User groups are teams of one or more researchers (users) led by a 'user group leader', also understood as principal investigator (PI) or chief scientist. A user group eligible for TA must meet the following **strict criteria**:

1. Affiliation/Country of work:

1.1 The user group leader (PI) and the majority of the users must work in a country other than the country(ies) where the installation is located (unless access is provided by an international organisation, the Joint Research Centre (JRC), an ERIC or similar legal entity).

1.2 The user group leader and the designated leader of the team conducting the fieldwork (also understood as chief/co-chief scientist) must be affiliated to the same institution.

2. International collaboration: Proposals for the AQUARIUS TA calls must involve at least three partners from three different countries.

3. Dissemination: Only user groups that are allowed to disseminate the results and knowledge they have generated in the context of the access may benefit from the TA, unless they are working for small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

4. Expertise: The user group leader (and designated chief scientist, if applicable) must have the appropriate scientific/ technical expertise to conduct proposed work.

5. European Mission Ocean 2030 Scientific challenges: User groups must make it clear how the proposed work contributes to selected priorities/challenges of the TA calls and the objectives of the European Mission Ocean 2030 according to AQUARIUS Deliverable 3.1 - AQUARIUS call priority and D6.1 – Data gaps report.

6. Access limit:

Access for user groups with a majority of users not working in a EU Member State or Horizon Europe associated country is limited to 20% of the total amount of units of access provided by AQUARIUS. I.e., at least 80% of the total units of access provided by the AQUARIUS project will be granted to parties with the majority of users working in a EU Member State or Horizon Europe associated country.

The non-fulfilment of any of the previous criteria implies the non-acceptance of the proposal for further evaluation.

4. Infrastructure offered within AQUARIUS

A new bespoke infrastructure catalogue will be available on the AQUARIUS website (<https://aquarius-ri.eu/ri-catalogue/>), which will provide instant access to detailed information on the infrastructure such as their scientific and technical capabilities.

The infrastructures offered in AQUARIUS (**Figure 2**) are categorised in the following nine categories:

- 1) Research Vessels
- 2) Marine Mobile Observation Platforms
- 3) Fixed Marine Facilities
- 4) Experimental Research Facilities
- 5) River & Basin Supersites
- 6) Aircrafts
- 7) Drones
- 8) Satellite Services
- 9) Data Centers & Virtual Labs

There is also a geographic element to the catalogue based on the concept of the Mission Lighthouses, where EU seas and major river basins are divided into four regions, each with a particular priority to be addressed:

- The Atlantic-Arctic and the Danube & Black Sea regions focus on protecting and restoring aquatic ecosystems.
- The Baltic & North Sea is focused on making the blue economy carbon neutral and circular.
- The Mediterranean Sea targets preventing and eliminating marine pollution.

Infrastructures in the catalogue are classified and can be filtered based on the lighthouse regions they serve.

Furthermore, the catalogue will provide clear information on the timing of infrastructure availability for those applying to one of the AQUARIUS calls.

In summary, the AQUARIUS Infrastructure Catalogue is poised to become an indispensable resource for researchers. By offering streamlined access to detailed information on scientific and technical capabilities, alongside geographic and thematic categorization, the catalogue ensures that applicants can swiftly identify the most suitable infrastructures for their research needs.

Additionally, the inclusion of availability timelines enhances the catalogue's utility, enabling researchers to align their proposals with the infrastructure's operational windows. This comprehensive approach not only simplifies the proposal process but also maximizes the impact of research by ensuring that the right tools are matched with the right missions.

Figure 2. Research Infrastructure offered within the AQUARIUS project.

A list of available infrastructures (sorted by type and operational area) offered in the TA calls, is available in **ANNEX 1**.

Figure 3 shows the percentage of RI offered in each Lighthouse Region.

Figure 3. Percentage of Research Infrastructure offered in the four Lighthouse Regions.

5. Funding and General conditions within AQUARIUS

Funding conditions

Funding is provided for accessing the Research Infrastructures owned by the AQUARIUS beneficiaries. Transnational access to the infrastructures offered in AQUARIUS is free of charge for the selected user groups. It covers the entire use of the infrastructures (in some cases with berth restrictions), including the logistical, technological, and scientific support for external researchers using the research infrastructure. Furthermore, it includes costs directly incurred to implement the project and other standard operating costs.

There is also a travel and logistics budget available with each infrastructure, which will contribute towards the user group's travel expenses and transport of equipment and samples. The amount can be negotiated after the positive scientific evaluation of the proposal depending on available resources.

The following costs are not eligible:

- Additional or third-party costs, such as salary costs or personnel costs of any kind, equipment manufacture, repair and rental of (scientific) equipment, subcontracting and assistance, vaccination and health care costs, publication costs and overheads.
- Insurance costs, or any extra costs of unforeseen circumstances related to travel (e.g. delays or cancellations), bar bills, and other extra services at the place of accommodation.

Detailed funding conditions are listed in deliverable 3.4 "Call documentation for the AQUARIUS Transnational Access Calls".

General conditions

- 1) **Ethical Standards:** Regarding the access to infrastructures and any research funded through AQUARIUS, facilitated or executed therein, the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon Europe will be rigorously applied, regardless of the country in which the research is carried out.

- 2) **Infrastructure Selection:** Users can select an unlimited number of infrastructures from the nine infrastructure categories offered as part of AQUARIUS. The selection and integration of at least two infrastructures from multiple categories is strongly encouraged.
- 3) **Training and Education:** Proposals are strongly encouraged to include an advanced training or educational element for scientists or technicians in their projects.
- 4) **Data Management Plans:** Funded TA research projects and user groups will implement data management plans (DMPs) for each TA project, which will be supervised and reviewed by assigned data centres. Researchers from the awarded projects will be educated in open science practices, European marine data infrastructures, and FAIR standards, services and tools to use for processing, documenting, and ingesting their newly collected data and resulting data products.

6. Evaluation

The AQUARIUS proposal evaluation system is based on evaluation structures, procedures and best practices from previous Transnational Access projects (e.g. EUROFLEETS 1, 2 & Plus; ARICE; INTERACCESS; JERICO, JERICO-NEXT, JERICO-S3 and ASSEMBLE Plus).

Proposals submitted to the AQUARIUS calls are evaluated in two steps:

1. **Scientific Evaluation:** Proposals are first evaluated scientifically by at least two scientific experts (referees). The evaluations are overseen by a Scientific Expert Panel, which ensures that the process is open, transparent, merit-based, impartial, and fair, strictly following the principles of equal opportunity. The panel also considers the alignment of the application with call topics and infrastructure integration. A consensus is reached by the Scientific Expert Panel as the final decision-making body.
2. **Logistical Feasibility Evaluation:** After the final recommendation of the Scientific Expert Panel, high-ranked proposals are examined by the AQUARIUS Operational Expert Panel to determine the logistical feasibility of the proposed work. The decisions are finalized by the infrastructure operators, based on the recommendations from both the Scientific and Operational Expert Panels.

This evaluation process ensures that only scientifically excellent proposals are considered for funding. The selection of user groups is based on scientific merit, and only those user-groups that are short-listed by the Scientific Expert Panel are considered for logistical evaluation and should benefit from the AQUARIUS Transnational Access.

Collaborative applications from user groups who have not previously used the requested research infrastructure(s) and where no equivalent research infrastructure exist, female, early career scientists, as well as an appropriate training aspect, are strongly encouraged. International and/or industrial partners are welcome.

AQUARIUS would promote and catalyze the integration of Ukrainian researchers and researchers with refugee status in the global marine research community; so, the participation of above-mentioned researches in the TA programme is strongly encouraged.

Proposals are invited to explore and support open science initiatives on a national and international level and to design and implement outreach activities, including citizen science initiatives as an area of application of open science.

ANNEX 1 - Table of the infrastructure offered, with direct links for each infrastructure to the online catalogue.

Type	Infrastructure	Provider	Country	Operational Area / Lighthouse Region(s)	Estimated Access Available ¹
1) Research Vessel	RV Gaia Blu	CNR	IT	Mediterranean Sea	10 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Sarmiento de Gamboa	CSIC	ES	Atlantic/Arctic, Mediterranean Sea	15 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Jákup Sverri	FMRI	DE	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea	15 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Mare Nigrum	GeoEcoMar	RO	Black Sea	10 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Sanna	GINR	GL	Atlantic/Arctic	15 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Aegaeo	HCMR	GR	Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea	15 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Thalassa	IFREMER	FR	Mediterranean Sea	15 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV L'Europe	IFREMER	FR	Atlantic/Arctic, Mediterranean Sea	10 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV G. O. Sars	IMR	NO	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea	10 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Arni Fridriksson	MFRI	IS	Atlantic/Arctic	10 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Celtic Explorer	MI	IE	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea	15 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Wim Wolff	NIOZ	NL	Baltic and North Sea	10 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Belgica	RBINS	BE	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea	15 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Svea	SLU	SE	Baltic and North Sea	10 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Socib	SOCIB	ES	Mediterranean Sea	10 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Aranda	SYKE	FI	Baltic and North Sea	12 Days

¹ The quantity of access is estimated and can be decreased or increased depending on scientific requirements, available resources and schedules. Each proposal will be logistically evaluated on a case-by-case basis and to align with the overall project resources available.

1) Research Vessel	RV Tubitak Marmara	TÜBİTAK Marmara	TR	Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea	10 Days
1) Research Vessel	RV Simon Stevin	VLIZ	BE	Baltic and North Sea	10 Days
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	Baltic Gliders	FMI	FI	Baltic and North Sea	100 Days
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	Max Rover	HCMR	GR	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea	4 Days
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	HROV ARIANE	IFREMER	FR	Atlantic/Arctic, Mediterranean Sea	8 Days
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	SmartBay Glider	MI	IE	Atlantic/Arctic	40 Days
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	NorSOOP	NIVA	NO	Baltic and North Sea, Atlantic/Arctic	40 Days
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	SOCIB Glider Facility	SOCIB	ES	Mediterranean Sea	100 Days
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	Alg@line	SYKE	FI	Baltic and North Sea	180 Days
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	UL-IROV	UL	IE	Atlantic/Arctic	14 Days
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	UL_MRE-ROV	UL	IE	Atlantic/Arctic	14 Days
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	AUV Barabas	VLIZ	BE	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea	15 Days
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	USV Adhemar	VLIZ	BE	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea	15 Days
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	Glider Yoko	VLIZ	BE	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea	30 Days
3) Fixed Marine Facility	W1M3A - Western Mediterranean Research Facility	CNR	IT	Mediterranean Sea	182 Days
3) Fixed Marine Facility	SiCO - Sicily Channel Observatory	CNR	IT	Mediterranean Sea	6 months
3) Fixed Marine Facility	CoCM - Corsica Channel Mooring	CNR	IT	Mediterranean Sea	6 months
3) Fixed Marine Facility	Utö Marine and Atmospheric Research Station	FMI	FI	Baltic and North Sea	100 Days
3) Fixed Marine Facility	POSEIDON	HCMR	GR	Mediterranean Sea	6 months
3) Fixed Marine Facility	Western Ionian Sea (WIS)	INGV	IT	Mediterranean Sea	80 Days
3) Fixed Marine Facility	SmartBay Observatory	MI	IE	Atlantic/Arctic	440 units x ports (5) per day
3) Fixed Marine Facility	SmartBay Buoy	MI	IE	Atlantic/Arctic	40 Days

3) Fixed Marine Facility	IMDBON	MI	IE	Atlantic/Arctic	365 Days
3) Fixed Marine Facility	South Adriatic Sea E2M3A EMSO Regional Facility	OGS	IT	Mediterranean Sea	182 Days
3) Fixed Marine Facility	PLOCAN Test Site	PLOCAN	ES	Atlantic/Arctic	20 Days
4) Experimental Research Facility	ISC-Lab	CNR	IT	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea	1 week
4) Experimental Research Facility	EMBCR (SBR)	EMBRC	FR	Atlantic/Arctic	90 Days per project
4) Experimental Research Facility	EMBCR (CCMAR)	EMBRC	FR	Atlantic/Arctic	60 Days per project
4) Experimental Research Facility	EMBCR (CIIMAR)	EMBRC	FR	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea	90 Days per project
4) Experimental Research Facility	EMBCR (IMEV)	EMBRC	FR	Mediterranean Sea	90 Days per project
4) Experimental Research Facility	EMBCR (OOB)	EMBRC	FR	Mediterranean Sea	90 Days per project
4) Experimental Research Facility	Lehanagh Pool	MI	IE	Atlantic/Arctic	60 Days
4) Experimental Research Facility	MI RAS	MI	IE	Atlantic/Arctic	60 Days
4) Experimental Research Facility	MESO & CAL	SYKE	FI	Baltic and North Sea	40 Days
5) River & Basin Supersite	EMSO-EUXINUS	GeoEcoMar	RO	Black Sea	2 Days
5) River & Basin Supersite	DANUBIUS-RI (Water Chemistry)	GeoEcoMar	ES	Black Sea	50 Samples
5) River & Basin Supersite	DANUBIUS-RI (Grainsize Mineralogy)	GeoEcoMar	BE	Black Sea	50 Samples
5) River & Basin Supersite	DANUBIUS-RI (Geochemistry)	GeoEcoMar	BE	Black Sea	50 Samples
5) River & Basin Supersite	DANUBIUS-RI (RV ISTROS)	GeoEcoMar	BE	Black Sea	15 Days
5) River & Basin Supersite	DANUBIUS-RI (Microplastics)	GeoEcoMar	BE	Black Sea	50 Samples
5) River & Basin Supersite	Elbe Supersite	HEREON	DE	Baltic and North Sea	1 Month
5) River & Basin Supersite	Burrishoole Catchment & Research Facility	MI	IE	Atlantic/Arctic	60 Days
5) River & Basin Supersite	iCIEM Ebro Delta Supersite	UPC	BE	Mediterranean Sea	2 months
6) Aircraft	FLIS	CzechGlobe	CZ	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea	20 Flight Hours

6) Aircraft	AIRS	OGS	IT	Mediterranean Sea	50 Flight Hours
6) Aircraft	CWIS-II (AVIRIS-4)	VITO	BE	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea	1 Flight Day
7) Drone	UL Drone	UL	IE	Atlantic/Arctic	14 Days
7) Drone	MAPEO	VITO	BE	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea	56 Flight Days
8) Satellite Service	Terrascope	VITO	BE	Atlantic/Arctic, Baltic and North Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea	10 areas of 10 tiles for 10 historic years